

Sustainable and Safe anode-free Na Battery

H2020-M-ERA.Net -3 Call 2021

Start date of the project: 01/09/2022

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D.1.1

Project partners

LOGO	Partner full name	Acronym
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	FZJ
	Altris AB	Altris
	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU
	PhaseTree	PT
	Uppsala University	UU
	ACCUREC Recycling GMBH	ACC

Deliverable Name: Creation of Image, website and social networks

Led by: CSIC

Participant partners:

Date	Version	Author	Institution	Comments*
30/10/2022	1	Ana L. Cudero	CSIC	Creation v1
20/02/2023	1	Ana L. Cudero	CSIC	Revision and inclusion of LinkedIn details

* Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
WP	Work package

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1. Introduction

Within the dissemination activities of the SuSaNa project in WP1, the creation of the branding image, logos and webpages was foreseen, as well as the inclusion of profile in social networks was proposed as a mean of reaching a greater public beyond the scientific community.

According to this, this deliverable of the project (D 1.1) gathers and presents all the above.

1.1. Logo

A dedicated logo for the project has been created by a brand designer and distributed among the partners. It is presented in *Figure 1*. This logo was chosen among different possibilities and voted by a majority of the partners.

The Logo combines the colours of a Green leaf, inspired by the concept of sustainability, and Orange in a sort of ray inspired by the concept energy. This forms a circle surrounding the Na in grey as the element sodium.

FIGURE 1: SUSANA PROJECT LOGO

The logo will be the visual identification of the project, and the rest of the image is constructed after the logo. It will be used in all the presentations and any time where the project is to be displayed

1.2. Templates

With this logo, a template for the preparation of the deliverables in format .doc has been distributed among the partners. The present document already complies with that format.

Presentations and other documents will also make use of the logo and brand image of the project. For that, a set of other templates for letters (.doc), presentations (power point) and reports (.doc) has also been prepared and distributed for its use by the partners along the project lifetime

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1.3. Webpage

A dedicated webpage has been designed as part of the dissemination activities, in accordance with the logo and general branding. The webpage site is: <https://susanaproject.csic.es/en>

The webpage is hosted by CSIC's, that offers free space for hosting web of projects.

A capture of the HOME page is presented in *Figure 2*.

FIGURE 2: SUSANA PROJECT WEBPAGE

The page has been divided in different sections (tabs), namely:

- ✓ **Home:** With a general description of the project
- ✓ **Project:** More detailed information of the project
- ✓ **Partners:** Direct link to the partner webpages
- ✓ **News/events:** Here all the events and news of the project will be gathered
- ✓ **Downloads:** Public document of general interest will be uploaded here
- ✓ **Contact:** form to get in contact with the coordinator.

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2. Social networks

With more and more people joining social media sites and using them regularly, the social media coverage is becoming unquestionable. Their use allows reaching a wider public with audiences beyond the project’s own community. The use of social network will include announcements to the general public of project meetings, attendance of the partners to workshops and conferences, news and announcements of the project and any new and/or event what could be potentially relevant to the SuSaNa project consortium.

Different social networks profiles have been created in a combination that is aimed to reach the widest possible audience, from purely scientific network such as ResearchGate, professional networks such as LinkedIn and general public such as Twitter.

2.1. ResearchGate

This network that gathers the scientific community is the perfect environment for scientific discussion and to share deep knowledge on the matter, such as scientific breakthroughs and advances. Within this network, the scientific publications, open source, will be shared.

The set profile in this network is the following: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Sustainable-and-Safe-anode-free-Na-battery-SuSaNa> and its preview is presented in *Figure 3*.

FIGURE 3: CAPTURE OF RESEARCHGATE PAGE FOR SUSANA PROJECT

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2.2. LinkedIn

This network gathers professionals from all sectors. A profile of the project has been created here with the aim of reaching professionals in the battery and related industries in order to raise awareness on potential future technologies such as the anode free Sodium ion battery that SuSaNa project aims to develop.

The LinkedIn profile address is <https://www.linkedin.com/company/susana-project/>

The page will be continuously fed with relevant news on the project and related technologies, in a professional language understandable for the professionals on the sector but also the general public. A preview is shown in *Figure 4*.

FIGURE 4: CAPTURE OF LINKEDIN PAGE FOR SUSANA PROJECT

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2.3. Twitter

Last but not least, a twitter account named **@SuSaNa_project** has been created in the most generalist network, Twitter. From this account general news and events will be released.

In addition, relevant news on the sector will be published here and it will serve also to spread the word about EU policies, batteries related news and other similar from official accounts (including, EU, EIC, CSIC, etc) or EU funded similar projects as a way to gain visibility towards the research results, the general field and the specific programs.

The twitter account is https://twitter.com/SuSaNa_project and a capture is presented in *Figure 5*.

FIGURE 5: CAPTURE OF TWITTER PAGE FOR SUSANA PROJECT

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3. Conclusions and final remarks

A variety of actions have been carried out in order to provide the due visibility and projection to the SuSaNA project.

Along with the creation of a logo and brand image of the project, different accounts in various networks have been set. All these accounts will be continuously fed in the frame of the diffusion activities of the project during and beyond the project life.

Especial use of these tools will be made whenever relevant news related of the project happens, such as project meetings, participation in events etc, as well as when any significant advance or breakthrough takes place.

Additionally, related news on the field of batteries, or related topics as well as other news regarding EU policies and M-ERA-Net will be shared from these accounts.

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